

Rac-11

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-5-rac-30%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	1003
Vial:	39	Acq. Method Set:	30%quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 160 5 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	316.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 316.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/3/2022 12:08:15 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/3/2022 2:47:06 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.164	672467	50.50	67595
2	6.262	659281	49.50	57970

Asy-11

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-160-5-asy-30%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	15	Acq. Method Set:	30%quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	xt 3 160 5
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	316.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 316.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/3/2022 9:42:39 AM CST		
Date Processed:	10/3/2022 11:49:46 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.232	28184	3.29	2342
2	6.341	828885	96.71	67982